

ADSORPTION METHODS OF CLEANING, DRYING AND DEBENZINIZING NATURAL GASES

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The reliability of operation of gas transportation systems (GTS), of which gas preparation units for transportation (UPGT) are an integral part, puts forward certain requirements for the quality of the transported gas. The main ones are the dew point for moisture and hydrocarbons.

In addition to methane, natural gas also contains heavier hydrocarbons (C_2-C_{7+}), water vapor and methanol. Sometimes inert gases, nitrogen (N_2) and carbon dioxide (CO_2) are present, as well as sulfur-containing components such as H_2S , organic sulfur compounds and small amounts of mercury and radioisotopes. When natural gas is supplied without prior purification, liquids may form in the gas transportation system. Hydrocarbons in the presence of water can form hydrates, which can clog valves and pipelines, and sometimes lead to emergency shutdowns. It is known that hydrates are the main cause of blockages in transportation systems [1].

The problems of drying natural gas with various adsorbents are considered in a number of publications, in particular, in works [2].

The feasibility of using one or another method of adsorption drying and purification of natural gas depends on many factors and is determined by the productivity of the plant, the composition of the gas, the concentration of hydrocarbons C_s , sulfur compounds and other impurities, and the consumer's requirements for purified gas.

- When solving specific practical problems related to gas purification and drying-stripping, it is necessary to take into account the main advantages of one or another adsorbent, such as [3-4]:

- ability to provide purification from all unwanted components in one system;

- providing deep gas drying;

- ease of operation and automation capability.

The adsorption process of drying hydrocarbon gases is widely used in gas processing plants as the first stage of low-temperature technology, the final products of which are liquefied gases such as propane, butane, liquid nitrogen and helium [1].

There is an opinion that the adsorption process of preparing gas for

processing is metal-intensive and expensive compared to, for example, the absorption process, which is widely used in fields. However, a higher degree of moisture extraction from gas and the absence of absorbent vapors in the dried gas, which can condense in the piping and apparatus during the gas cooling process (not to mention entrainment), make this process reliable, stimulate its improvement and wide application in industrial gas processing.

As for the industrial preparation of gas for transportation through main gas pipelines, the main criterion for choosing a preparation method is the dew point of the gas for moisture and hydrocarbons, which eliminates their condensation and precipitation in gas pipelines [1, 3].

The main adsorbents used for cleaning and drying-stripping of natural gases in industry are [4]:

- active carbons;
- zeolites;
- active aluminum oxide;
- silica gels.

On their basis, a number of technologies for cleaning, drying and stripping of natural gas have been developed and introduced into industry.

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